

Research paper

Design and application of a dissolution-permeation apparatus with scalable surface area and controllable hydrodynamic conditions at the membrane interface

David Zůza^a, Doreen Pritts^a, Vojtěch Klimša^a, Josef Beránek^b, František Štěpánek^{a,*}

^a University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Department of Chemical Engineering, Technická 3, Praha 166 28, Czech Republic

^b Zentiva, k.s., U Kabelovny 130, 102 00 Praha 10, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Dissolution
Permeation
Drug absorption
Membrane area
Unstirred water layer
Apparent permeability
Rate-limiting step
Enabling formulations

ABSTRACT

The evaluation of drug release from enabling formulations often requires a coupled measurement of dissolution and permeation processes. While dissolution testing alone is well established in pharmaceutical development, coupled dissolution-permeation studies often face challenges due to limited permeation surface area and poor control over local hydrodynamic conditions that affect the thickness of the unstirred water layer at the membrane interface. This study presents a dissolution-permeation device integrating a standard USP II dissolution vessel and a custom-built permeation module with a sandwich structure, offering a permeation area that is scalable by multiplication. The functionality of the apparatus was demonstrated using carboxyfluorescein and caffeine as model solutes permeating across polycarbonate and polyvinylidene fluoride membranes under varying hydrodynamic conditions. The results provide a clear dependence of the apparent permeability on the flow velocity at the membrane interface, indicating a significant influence of the unstirred water layer. Simultaneous dissolution-permeation experiments with tablet prototypes exhibiting immediate and sustained drug release demonstrated the ability of the device to capture dynamic permeation behaviour, revealing an initial non-steady permeation phase that transitions into pseudo steady-state conditions. It has been shown that the permeation flux can be increased by multiplication of the basic permeation module to increase the membrane area to 100 cm². The findings establish the apparatus as a platform suitable for dynamic *in vitro* dissolution-permeation experiments with a potential to support formulation development and provide data for *in-vivo-in-vitro* correlations.

1. Introduction

Dissolution and permeation studies are key tools in pharmaceutical development, providing insights into drug release, solubility, absorption, and ultimately bioavailability [1–6]. Dissolution testing measures the rate at which a drug is released into a dissolution medium from its dosage form, while permeation studies measure the ability of the drug to cross biological membranes or their *in vitro* models. When dissolution and permeation processes occur on different time scales, they can be studied separately using dedicated experimental devices. Dissolution is standardized in the United States Pharmacopoeia (USP), with the paddle method (USP Apparatus II) being the most widely used [7,8]. Permeability assays such as the parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA) [9] or live cell-based Caco-2 [10] or MDCK [11] assays are

common, but they generally require pre-dissolved drug and often underestimate permeability due to diffusion limitations in the unstirred water layer [12]. Enabling formulations such as amorphous solid dispersions, self-emulsifying drug delivery systems, or nanocrystal suspensions often necessitate the coupling of dissolution and permeation processes to mimic absorption by the removal of a supersaturating drug from the dissolution compartment. The appropriate choice of the permeation barrier is important for the biorelevance of such experiments; a recent head-to-head comparison of commonly used membrane barriers can be found in reference [13].

For the reason stated above, there is an increasing interest in the development of devices that combine dissolution and permeation into an integrated system [14]. Such hybrid devices aim to improve the biorelevance of *in vitro* models, ultimately reducing reliance on animal

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Frantisek.Stepanek@vscht.cz (F. Štěpánek).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2026.115074>

Received 8 December 2025; Received in revised form 29 March 2026; Accepted 12 April 2026

Available online 13 April 2026

0939-6411/© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. a) Scheme of the dissolution-permeation apparatus (1 – dissolution vessels, 2 – permeation module, 3 – quick connectors, 4 – valves for emptying or bypass, 5 – peristaltic pumps for media recirculation, 6 – stirrers). b) Detail of the permeation module (1 – polycarbonate side cover panel, 2 – silicon spacer plate, 3 – membrane). c) Complete dissolution-permeation apparatus with housing and a touch-screen control panel; the inset shows two permeation modules connected in parallel to double the membrane area.

testing and supporting alignment with regulatory expectations [15–20]. Existing solutions include the MicroFLUX™, MakroFLUX™, and BioFLUX™ systems (Pion, Inc.), which use standard USP vessels enhanced by a permeation module that is either directly inserted into the dissolution vessel or adjacent to it [21–23]. The modules use proprietary membranes with an area of 3.88 cm², which may or may not provide a sufficiently high permeation flux when studying e.g. supersaturating formulations. A flow-through system Permealoop™ [4,6] offers a substantially larger permeation area (~28 cm²) and flexible membrane options. Its reported area-to-volume ratio (1.38 cm⁻¹) is considered more biorelevant than previously used permeation assays, though the absolute quantity permeated depends on additional factors such as the API and the membrane choice.

The area-to-volume ratio is a critical parameter for the physiological relevance of coupled dissolution-permeation tests. Standard *in vitro* dissolution volumes (200–900 mL) are comparable to stomach conditions [24], whereas *in vitro* membrane areas are much lower than the human intestinal surface area, reported to be tens to hundreds of m² depending on how the microvilli are counted [25,26]. It has been estimated that only about 7 m² is actively involved in absorption at any time during the transit of a disintegrated solid dosage form through the gastrointestinal tract (2–6 h) [27,28], and the effective area may drop to 1–2 m² in some instances [29–31]. Thus, using *in vitro* membranes with a higher permeability than the human intestine, even modest permeation areas (around 100 cm²) could adequately mimic gastrointestinal absorption fluxes when combined with standard 900 mL dissolution vessels.

Apart from the surface area, the permeation flux also depends on the local hydrodynamic conditions near the membrane interface. The so-called unstirred water layer (UWL) [12] represents an additional barrier to solute diffusion, and its resistance can be comparable to that of the membrane itself given that the UWL is present on both the donor and the acceptor side of the membrane. The thickness of the UWL depends on the local fluid flow velocity at the membrane interface. The resistance due to UWL could be reduced or even eliminated if the local fluid velocity could be increased sufficiently. However, when the permeation membrane is integrated directly into the dissolution compartment, the interfacial fluid velocity cannot be controlled independently of the dissolution stirring rate. Even with external recirculation, the maximum attainable flowrate is usually limited. The aim of the present study, therefore, was to introduce a dissolution–permeation apparatus designed to enable modular scale-up of the permeation area and independent control of hydrodynamic conditions at the membrane interface, along with a methodology for the evaluation of permeability by controlling and quantifying the influence of the UWL. Such a set-up can be used for removing a portion of the dissolved API during a dissolution experiment and thus explore various scenarios *in vitro* and test formulation where coupled dissolution and permeation may be relevant.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Device design and construction

The device for simultaneous dissolution and permeation measurement is based on two stirred dissolution vessels (USP type II) that act as the donor and the acceptor of the permeant, respectively, coupled via a mass-transfer module as depicted in Fig. 1. The permeation module is designed to enable the scale-up of surface area by multiplication, and the control of hydrodynamic conditions at the membrane by setting the flowrate of recirculation pumps independently of the stirring rate in the dissolution vessels. The planar membrane modules (Fig. 1b) have a sandwich structure to accommodate either commercially available or in-house developed membranes that can be freely chosen according to the purpose of the permeation experiment. The permeation modules are autoclavable to facilitate sterile operation when using cell-based membranes or *ex vivo* organoids (examples are shown in the Supplementary

Material).

The donor and acceptor reservoirs are standard 900 mL dissolution vessels (Vankel) modified by the addition of an outlet port at the bottom and an inlet port placed 8 cm from the lip of the vessel. These modifications were made either by professional glasswork or by drilling a hole in the vessel and 3D printing a housing to screw in a ¼-inch inlet. The stirrer for dissolution vessels is a Witeg HT50DX paddle stirrer. Stirrers in the donor and the acceptor vessels are connected by a 1:1 chain gear mounted by a 3D printed housing with 10 mm ball bearings. The frame of the apparatus is assembled from ITEM extruded aluminium profiles (Fig. 1a). The dissolution vessels are connected to the permeation module by silicon tubing using quick connectors and stop valves for comfortable filling, emptying, and rinse cleaning of the device without disassembly. Samples of the donor and the acceptor media can be taken either from the dissolution vessels or from the respective recirculation loops. The acceptor medium can be either recirculated or continuously withdrawn and replenished with a fresh medium to maintain sink conditions if required.

The permeation module is placed below the dissolution vessels (Fig. 1) to ensure identical hydrostatic pressure at both sides of the membrane. This minimises any convective contribution to the trans-membrane flux. Before each experimental run, the liquid level in each vessel was marked and it has been verified that no liquid leaked into the opposite compartment during the measurement. The recirculation pumps are connected downstream from the permeation module to avoid pressure fluctuations across the membrane. The pumps utilized in the device are Kamoer KCM-B146 peristaltic pumps based on the NEMA motor. The pumps are controlled by an Arduino ESP board with an A4988 driver for each pump. The following parameters can be set via a touch screen: forward and backward movement, automatic micro-stepping, automatic ramp-up of revolutions at the start and ramp-down at the finish of the experiment (ensuring the motor does not seize), flowrate in the range 30–105 mL/min (corresponding to 200–700 rpm), temperature, and time scheduling. A resistance heater with a temperature controller is installed on the recirculation loop. The dead volume of the connecting pipes plus the internal volume of a the permeation cell is approximately 50 mL on one side, which effectively reduces the volume in the dissolution vessel.

The design of the permeation module (Fig. 1b) is based on a plate mass exchanger with a sandwich structure, as it is scalable by multiplication and can accommodate a range of commercial or custom-made membrane types, which are often available in sheets. The side cover panels of the permeation module are made from polycarbonate. The entire sandwich structure is fitted and sealed together by screws with fly nuts for easy assembly and uniform contact force. The membrane is sealed between a pair of silicon spacers that define the geometry of the flow channels on each side of the membrane. These spacers were prepared by silicon casting into 3D printed moulds; thus, the internal geometry of the flow channels can be modified easily. The channel geometry was motivated by the goal to control the hydrodynamic conditions at the membrane interface and thus the unstirred water layer. Ideally, the tangential velocity distribution should be as narrow as possible. The chosen design, supported by CFD simulations, was a meandering channel with a constant rectangular cross-section (6 mm height, 14 mm width). The membrane area available for permeation was either 34.4 cm² or 50.0 cm² per module depending on the total channel length. The total permeation area can be multiplied by connecting multiple modules in series or in parallel as shown in Fig. 1c.

2.2. Materials

Caffeine, 5,6-carboxyfluorescein (≥95% purity) and phosphate buffered saline (PBS) tablets were purchased from Merck. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose phthalate (HPMCP E3), microcrystalline cellulose grade (MCC, Avicel PH-101) and croscarmellose sodium were kindly provided by Zentiva, k.s. Deionised water (0.08 μS cm⁻¹) was

Table 1
Properties of membranes used for permeation experiments.

Material	PVDF	PC
Affinity	hydrophilic	hydrophilic
Thickness	125 μm	25 μm
Pore size	0.22 μm	0.8 μm
Porosity	70 %	5–20 %
Air penetrability	2.0 L min ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	4.08 L min ⁻¹ cm ⁻²

Fig. 2. Scheme of a theoretical concentration profile across a porous hydrophilic membrane illustrating the presence of the unstirred water layer (UWL) and its impact on the apparent permeability (P_{app}) in comparison to the membrane (intrinsic) permeability. C_D and C_A denote the concentration of molecularly dissolved solute in the donor and the acceptor medium, respectively.

produced by the Aqual 25 ion exchange device. Membranes for permeation studies – a polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membrane sold under the trade name Durapore® – and a polycarbonate (PC) membrane sold under the trade name Isopore® – were purchased from Merck as a stack of circular sheets with a diameter of 142 mm from which the required rectangular membranes were cut. The properties of both membranes are listed in Table 1. The rationale behind the choice of these simple porous membranes was to achieve as high permeation fluxes as possible, to test the limits of the dissolution-permeation apparatus. Other membrane types such as lipid-coated PAMPA or PVPA membranes could be used for other experiments whose aim might be different.

2.3. Methodology of permeation measurement

The dissolution-permeation device described above was used in two modes: (i) permeation-only experiments that start from pre-dissolved solutes in the donor compartment, and (ii) coupled dissolution-permeation experiments during which drug release from the tested formulation in the donor compartment occurs simultaneously with permeation into the acceptor compartment. The permeation-only experiments were designed to validate the reproducibility of the

measurement and to quantify the impact of hydrodynamic conditions in the permeation module on the apparent permeability and the effect of the unstirred water layer on the permeation rate. The dissolution-permeation experiments were then conducted to test whether the rate of solute withdrawal by permeation can match the rate of dissolution.

As shown schematically in Fig. 2, the driving force for permeation is the concentration gradient between the donor and the acceptor medium, which acts over the combined resistance of the membrane and the unstirred water layer (UWL) present on each side of the membrane. Considering the additivity principle of resistances in series, the apparent permeability P_{app} is related to the membrane permeability P_{mem} [32] (sometimes also called “intrinsic” permeability) and the mass-transfer coefficients k_{UWL} on each side of the membrane according to

$$\frac{1}{P_{app}} = \frac{1}{P_{mem}} + \frac{1}{k_{UWL,donor}} + \frac{1}{k_{UWL,acceptor}} \quad (1)$$

The thickness of the unstirred water layer depends on the hydrodynamic conditions near the membrane and diminishes with increasing flowrate, i.e. $1/k_{UWL} \rightarrow 0$ for $1/Re \rightarrow 0$ where Re is the local Reynolds number defined by

$$Re = \frac{uh\rho}{\eta} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), u is the fluid velocity, h is the characteristic dimension (here the channel height), ρ is the fluid density and η is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid. By measuring the apparent permeability for a series of flowrates and extrapolating to $1/Re = 0$, the terms $1/k_{UWL}$ on the right-hand side of Eq. (1) will diminish and the value of the membrane permeability can be determined. Note that here we adopt chemical engineering terminology, but the mass-transfer coefficient k_{UWL} is also known as “UWL permeability” [33]. Its value can be estimated from established mass-transfer correlations for laminar flow along a planar surface [34] according to:

$$Sh = 0.664Re^{1/2}Sc^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

where

$$Sh = \frac{hk_{UWL}}{D} = \frac{h}{\delta_{UWL}} \quad (4)$$

and

$$Sc = \frac{\eta}{\rho D} \quad (5)$$

are the Sherwood and the Schmidt numbers, respectively. In the equations above, D is the molecular diffusivity of the solute, δ_{UWL} is the thickness of the unstirred water layer, and remaining variables are the same as in the Reynolds number defined by Eq. (2).

When testing or comparing pharmaceutical formulations that

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration of the procedure used for calculating the membrane permeability. a) Measurement of permeation flux at a given recirculation flowrate using donor solution with pre-dissolved drug donor sol; b) calculation of the apparent permeability for each flowrate from the permeation flux; c) determination of the membrane permeability by extrapolation to infinite flowrate.

contain different concentrations of polymeric excipients or the same polymeric excipient with different viscosity grades, it is important to keep in mind that even if the flowrate in the channel of a permeation cell is kept constant, the Reynolds number may still be different due to different fluid properties (density and viscosity), and so is the UWL thickness. Therefore, quantifying the UWL effect by systematically changing hydrodynamic conditions at the membrane is rather important for the correct interpretation of data when comparing different pharmaceutical formulations or different dissolution media.

The overall procedure for determining the membrane permeability is shown schematically in Fig. 3. For a given flowrate through the permeation cell, solute concentration in the donor and the acceptor medium was determined from samples taken at prescribed time intervals (Fig. 3a). After completing one round of sampling, the flowrate was set to a new value, and the process was repeated (Fig. 3b). The apparent permeability P_{app} for a given flowrate was calculated from its definition according to

$$P_{app} = \frac{J}{\Delta c} \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta c = \bar{c}_D - \bar{c}_A$ is the mean concentration driving force over a given time interval, expressed as the difference between molecularly dissolved solute concentration in the donor and the acceptor medium, respectively, and J ($\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) is the permeation mass flux defined by

$$J = \frac{1}{A} \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta t} \quad (7)$$

In Eq. (7), A (cm^2) is the membrane area available for permeation and $\Delta m/\Delta t$ (mg s^{-1}) is the mass of solute permeated per unit time, determined from the slope of the cumulative permeated mass over the measurement period (Fig. 3b). Finally, the membrane permeability was obtained from the apparent permeability values by extrapolation to infinite flowrate (Fig. 3c), using inverted flowrate as the independent variable (thus P_{app} can be conveniently determined as an intercept with the y-axis).

2.4. Permeation-only experiments

The permeation-only experiment proceeded as follows. First, both donor and acceptor compartments were filled with 600 mL of media. The donor medium was either a 0.1 mg mL^{-1} solution of caffeine in PBS pH 7.4 or a 0.05 mg mL^{-1} solution of 5,6-carboxyfluorescein in PBS pH 7.4. The acceptor medium was PBS pH 7.4. The paddle stirring rate was 50 rpm in both vessels and temperature was set to 25 °C. The recirculation volumetric flowrate was gradually set to several values in the range from 30 mL min^{-1} to 105 mL min^{-1} using a pre-calibrated dependence between the rpm of the peristaltic pumps and the volumetric flowrate. These volumetric flowrates correspond to mean fluid velocities in the channel (rectangular cross section with $h = 6$ mm and $w = 14$ mm) ranging between 0.0060–0.0208 m s^{-1} and shear rates in the range from 1.00 s^{-1} to 3.47 s^{-1} . The Reynolds numbers (for a density of 1000 kg m^{-3} and dynamic viscosity 10^{-3} Pa s) thus varied between 36 and 125, i.e. in the laminar regime. Achieving turbulence in small channels (characteristic dimensions in mm's) would require flowrates at least two to three orders of magnitude higher, which is unrealistic.

For a given recirculation flowrate, samples from the donor and the acceptor medium were taken at predetermined time intervals (typically 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 min or longer depending on the overall permeation rate for a given solute). The solute concentration in the collected samples was determined by UV/Vis spectrophotometry with three replicates using previously constructed calibration curves (details are provided in the Supplementary Material). The concentration series for each flowrate were then processed as described in Section 2.3 to obtain the membrane permeability.

2.5. Validation of experimental reproducibility

To verify that the device provides consistent results and the measurement procedure is robust, an experiment with caffeine across a PVDF membrane at a flowrate of 90 mL min^{-1} was carried out as described in Section 2.4 (except for sampling times, which were 0, 6, 12, 18, 24 and 30 min) and repeated three times. The device was stopped, rinsed and cleaned after each 30-minute permeation run to provide three independent permeation sets. The mean and the standard deviation of each concentration point as well as the apparent permeability were then evaluated from the three independent experiments.

2.6. Coupled dissolution-permeation measurement

To test the ability of the device to capture differences in drug release profiles from different formulations, two kinds of caffeine tablets – further called “fast-dissolving” and “slowly-dissolving” – were prepared. The fast-dissolving tablet contained microcrystalline cellulose as a filler and croscarmellose sodium as a disintegrant. The slowly dissolving tablet contained HPMCP as a gel forming polymer, and no disintegrant. The exact composition of the tablets is given in Table 2. Powders were weighted for each tablet individually, homogenised and tableted on a Natoli NP-RD10A hydraulic tablet press using 8 mm diameter cylindrical dies with flat-face punches and a compression force of 40 kN.

During the dissolution-permeation experiment, both compartments were filled with 600 mL of PBS pH 7.4. The paddle stirring rate was 50 rpm in both vessels and temperature was set to 25 °C. The tested flowrates were 45 mL min^{-1} and 90 mL min^{-1} for both types of tablets. The experiments were named accordingly: FDT45, FDT90, SDT45 and SDT90 for the fast- and the slowly dissolving tablets, respectively. The PVDF membrane was used. Sampling from both the donor and the acceptor medium was conducted simultaneously at 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50 and 60 min. Caffeine concentrations were determined by UV/Vis spectrophotometry (cf. Supplementary Material) and the permeation flux was evaluated according to Eq. Eq (7).

2.7. Scale-up of permeation area

A coupled dissolution-permeation experiment is meaningful only when the permeation rate can keep up with the dissolution rate, i.e. when the cumulative quantity permeated over the time scale of dissolution is at least several 10's % of the dose, not a few 1's %. Otherwise, dissolution and permeation experiments could be performed separately. To test the ability of the dissolution-permeation apparatus to achieve large permeation fluxes, the following experiment was conducted. Two permeation modules in parallel were connected to the dissolution vessels (cf. Fig. 1c), providing a total permeation area of 100 cm^2 ; a PVDF membrane was used. Both compartments were filled with 700 mL of PBS pH 7.4, the paddle stirring rate was 50 rpm in both vessels and temperature was set to 37 °C. The recirculation flowrate was set to 90 mL min^{-1} . To simulate fast drug release and a high concentration driving force as might occur for supersaturating drug formulations, 200 mg of caffeine in a powder form was dosed into the donor compartment at once. Samples were collected from the donor and the acceptor compartment at predetermined time points between 0 and 120 min and processed as described above.

Table 2

Composition of caffeine tablets used in coupled dissolution-permeation experiments.

Component	Fast-dissolving tablet (FDT) [mg]	Slowly dissolving tablet (SDT) [mg]
Caffeine	60	60
Avicel PH-101	450	0
Croscarmellose sodium	50	0
HPMCP E3	0	500
Total	560	560

Fig. 4. Cumulative mass permeated as a function of time for caffeine across a PVDF membrane at 25 °C and a flowrate of 90 mL min⁻¹, initial donor concentration 0.1 mg mL⁻¹. The data points represent mean values, and the error bars represent standard deviations (N = 3).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Repeatability of experiments

The repeatability of the experimental procedure was tested using caffeine on a PVDF membrane as described in Section 2.5 above. The cumulative quantity permeated as a function of time for a flowrate of 90 mL/min is plotted in Fig. 4. The data points represent mean values and the error bars denote standard deviations based on three independent experimental runs with device emptying and rinsing in between each

set. The apparent permeability values $\log P_{app}$ evaluated from each experiment separately according to Eqs. (6) and (7) were -3.790 , -3.791 and -3.811 log(cm/s), respectively, which indicates excellent repeatability of the experimental procedure and robustness of the method by which permeability was evaluated. It should be noted that the absolute mass of caffeine permeated during a 30 min time interval was approximately 1 mg out of 60 mg initially present in the donor medium, which means the concentration driving force remained essentially unchanged and the $\Delta m/\Delta t$ term in Eq. (7) could be obtained by linear regression over the entire interval as shown in Fig. 4.

3.2. Effect of flowrate on permeation

The permeation rate of two solutes (caffeine and carboxyfluorescein) across two membranes (PVDF and PC) was evaluated according to the methodology described in Section 2.4. The cumulative mass permeated for each solute on each membrane for a range of flowrates is summarised in Fig. 5. The experiments for the PVDF membrane (Fig. 5a and b) were conducted as two independent runs of three flowrates each, namely 30, 60, and 105 mL min⁻¹ for the first run, and 45, 75, and 90 mL min⁻¹ for the second run. This approach served as an additional validation of the reproducibility and robustness of the experimental procedure, as when permeation data from both sets were combined, they formed a self-consistent series (shown in Fig. 6a for caffeine and Fig. 6b for carboxyfluorescein).

All four sets of experimental permeation data shown in Fig. 5 clearly revealed the effect of the unstirred water layer (UWL) and its decreasing resistance with increasing flowrate (cf. Section 2.3). It follows from these experiments that simply reporting one-point values of the apparent permeability without systematically measuring its dependence

Fig. 5. The cumulative mass permeated as function time, measured at increasing flowrate through the permeation module as indicated in the legend of each chart. a) Caffeine across PVDF membrane; b) carboxyfluorescein across PVDF membrane; c) caffeine across PC membrane; d) carboxyfluorescein across PC membrane.

Fig. 6. Evaluation of the membrane permeability by extrapolation to infinite flowrate based on permeation data reported in Fig. 5. a) Caffeine across PVDF membrane; b) carboxyfluorescein across PVDF membrane; c) caffeine across PC membrane; d) carboxyfluorescein across PC membrane.

Table 3

Values of membrane permeability of both solutes on both membranes obtained by extrapolation to infinite flowrate. The effective diffusion coefficient through the membrane was calculated from P_{mem} and the membrane thickness (given in Table 1) in each case.

	$\log P_{mem}$ [log(cm/s)]	D_{eff} [m ² /s]
Caffeine on PVDF	-3.63	2.9×10^{-10}
Caffeine on PC	-3.12	1.9×10^{-10}
Carboxyfluorescein on PVDF	-3.72	2.4×10^{-10}
Carboxyfluorescein on PC	-3.70	0.5×10^{-10}

on the hydrodynamic conditions may not be very meaningful. Permeability values reported in the literature rarely contain information about the hydrodynamic conditions under which they were obtained. As shown in a recent review, permeability values published by different authors for the same molecule can differ even by several orders of magnitude [35].

The effect of the UWL can be eliminated by extrapolation to an infinite flowrate. This is shown for all four solute-membrane combinations in Fig. 6 where the membrane permeability $\log P_{mem}$ was determined as an intercept with the y-axis (blue point in each chart). The values of $\log P_{mem}$ obtained by extrapolation for all four solute-membrane combinations are summarised in Table 3. The two membranes differ in both structure (porosity, pore size, membrane thickness) and chemical composition, which means that each permeating solute can interact differently with each membrane. While the PC membrane is thinner and has larger pores, it also has lower porosity than the PDVF membrane (Table 1). Hence, it could not be stated *a priori* which membrane should provide a higher permeability for a given solute. In the case of caffeine, the membrane permeability was lower on the PVDF membrane compared to the PC membrane. In the case of

carboxyfluorescein, it appears that the properties of both membranes just happened to counteract each other, resulting in similar membrane permeability values (Table 3).

For reference, the effective diffusivity of each solute in each membrane was calculated from the P_{mem} values and included in Table 3 from membrane thickness provided by the membrane suppliers (cf. Table 1). For comparison, the bulk molecular diffusivity of carboxyfluorescein and caffeine in water at 25 °C is $0.425 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $0.749 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively.

From Eqs. (2)–(5) the thickness of the UWL can be estimated. For the range of flowrates investigated here (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6), i.e. 30–105 mL/min, the mean fluid velocity in the channel of the permeation cell was $u = 0.0060\text{--}0.0208 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, the Reynolds number was $Re = 36\text{--}125$, the resulting Sherwood number was $Sh = 46\text{--}101$, and the mass transfer coefficient was therefore $k_{UWL} = 4.7\text{--}8.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. Given the channel height of $h = 6 \text{ mm}$ and caffeine diffusion coefficient of $D_{caf} = 0.749 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, the unstirred water layer thickness could be estimated in the range $\delta_{UWL} = 68\text{--}130 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Note that this is comparable with the thickness of the membranes themselves (Table 1).

3.3. Simultaneous dissolution and permeation

The tablet preparation and the experiment were performed as described in Section 2.6. Every experiment was conducted separately with a fresh membrane. As each tablet contained 60 mg of caffeine and the volume of the dissolution medium was 600 mL, the theoretical maximum donor concentration upon complete dissolution of the dose would be 0.1 mg mL^{-1} , i.e. identical to the experiments with pre-dissolved caffeine discussed in the previous section. The dissolution profiles based on sampling from the donor compartment are shown in Fig. 7a and the cumulative mass permeated into the acceptor medium is plotted in Fig. 7b. Both quantities were expressed as percentage of the

Fig. 7. Combined dissolution-permeation experiments for fast-dissolving (FDT) and slowly dissolving (SDT) tablets at flowrates of 45 and 90 mL min⁻¹. a) Release profiles of caffeine in the donor compartment; b) cumulative mass permeated into the acceptor compartment; c) instantaneous apparent permeability. All concentrations are expressed as percentage of the total dose, which was 60 mg. Other experimental conditions are specified in Section 2.6.

dose. The dissolution profiles clearly show the differences in drug release from the fast-dissolving (FDT) and slowly dissolving tablets (SDT). FDT's exhibited the characteristics of an immediate release formulation, with more than 90 % of the dose dissolved in 15 min. SDT's displayed the characteristics of a sustained release formulation, with a zero-order release profile and approx. 50% drug released in 60 min (Fig. 7a).

The quantity of caffeine permeated as a function of time, shown in Fig. 7b, was strongly influenced by the concentration driving force set by dissolution in the donor compartment. For FDT's, the tablets were fully dissolved within 15–20 min and the maximum possible concentration driving force was reached. From approximately that point onward, permeation behaved the same as from pre-dissolved caffeine. The permeation flux was systematically higher for a 90 mL min⁻¹ flowrate than for 45 mL min⁻¹ due to lower resistance of the unstirred water layer, and the two permeation curves diverged (Fig. 7b). For the fast-dissolving tablets, the rate-limiting step for drug absorption into the acceptor medium was permeation across the membrane rather than drug

Table 4

Comparison of the apparent permeability of caffeine on PVDF membrane evaluated from three different experiments: pre-dissolved caffeine, dissolution-permeation from slowly dissolving tablets (SDT), and dissolution-permeation from fast-dissolving tablets (FDT). For dissolution-permeation experiments the values are based on four time points in the 30–60 min interval.

Experiment	logP _{app} [log(cm/s)]
SDT45	-3.93 ± 0.01
FDT45	-3.94 ± 0.02
Pre-dissolved (45 mL min ⁻¹)	-3.94
SDT90	-3.80 ± 0.03
FDT90	-3.84 ± 0.02
Pre-dissolved (90 mL min ⁻¹)	-3.78

release from the dosage form.

In the case of slowly dissolving tablets, the permeation rate was visibly limited by the available concentration driving force. After an initial transient period of approx. 30–40 min, both SDT permeation curves had the same slope, which indicates that reducing the UWL resistance by increasing flowrate from 45 to 90 mL min⁻¹ did not result in an improvement of the permeation rate (Fig. 7b). It can be concluded that the rate-limiting step for drug absorption into the acceptor medium was drug release from the dosage form rather than permeation. The ability of the dissolution-permeation device to capture both regimes – drug absorption limited by dissolution vs. drug absorption limited by permeation – makes it a useful tool for comparing formulation prototypes during drug development.

When the apparent permeability was evaluated from the combined dissolution-permeation experiment at various time intervals (Fig. 7c), all four cases appeared to converge towards values that were remarkably consistent with P_{app} obtained during experiments from pre-dissolved caffeine at the corresponding flowrate. All values are summarised in Table 4. Once the concentration driving force was factored in, the apparent permeabilities obtained for each flowrate were closely aligned irrespective of the nature of the experiment (pre-dissolved caffeine, slowly dissolving and fast-dissolving tablets). This further underlines the robustness of the dissolution-permeation apparatus.

3.4. Scale-up of permeation area

The previous section demonstrated the ability to conduct simultaneous dissolution-permeation experiments, but the quantity permeated over the duration of the experiment was relatively modest under the experimental conditions used, representing only 2.5 % of the dose even

Fig. 8. Progress of caffeine concentration in the donor and acceptor media during a coupled dissolution-permeation experiment with scaled-up permeation area. Concentrations in the donor and the acceptor phase were measured independently; the Total is a check of mass balance.

in the fastest case (FDT90). Consequently, the concentration profile in the donor medium was essentially unaffected by permeation. To test a scenario where permeation can withdraw a more substantial fraction of the dose, as would be desirable during the testing of various enabling formulations, a dissolution-permeation experiment was conducted as described in Section 2.7. The main differences from previous experiments were higher temperature (37 °C), higher dose (200 mg) to create a higher concentration driving force in the donor medium, and a scaled-up permeation area (100 cm² achieved by connecting two permeation cells in series). The diffusivity of caffeine in water at 25 °C and 37 °C is $0.749 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $1.021 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively [36], which means temperature alone could be expected to increase the permeation rate by approx. 36 %. The surface area was increased from 34.4 cm² to 100 cm², causing an expected increase of permeation rate by 190 %.

The evolution of caffeine concentration in the donor and the acceptor media (expressed as a percentage of the dose) is shown in Fig. 8. The caffeine concentration in the donor medium initially increased according to its release kinetics from the dosage form, but the fraction dissolved reached a maximum at approx. 35 min and then monotonously decreased as permeation of the dissolved caffeine dominated. The mass of caffeine permeated in 120 min was 37 mg (18.5 % of dose), which already represents a physiologically meaningful quantity for many drugs. The increased permeation flux also caused the donor concentration profile to go through a characteristic maximum, which results from the superposition two fluxes with opposite signs: one positive (drug release from the dosage form) and one negative (permeation to the acceptor medium) similarly to what might occur in the gastrointestinal tract. Note that this scenario is different to permeation-only experiments from pre-dissolved API considered in Section 3.2, where concentration in the donor decreased monotonously from time zero. The apparent permeability of caffeine across a PVDF membrane evaluated from the dissolution-permeation experiment with a scaled-up surface area was $\log P_{\text{app}} = -3.75$, which is consistent with values obtained for the same solute-membrane combination earlier and reported in Table 4.

4. Conclusion

A dissolution-permeation device combining a standard USP II dissolution apparatus with a custom-designed flow-through permeation module has been constructed and tested. The main features of the device include a flat-sheet membrane module with a sandwich structure, that allows the scale-up of the permeation area by multiplication, and the ability to control the hydrodynamic conditions at the membrane interface independently from the stirring rate in the dissolution vessel. This makes it possible to control and quantify the thickness of the unstirred water layer at the membrane interface and thus assess its effect on the overall permeability for a given drug-membrane combination.

This has been demonstrated using two different model solutes (caffeine and carboxyfluorescein) on two different membranes (PVDF and polycarbonate). It has been concluded that the methodology presented in this work can provide robust and consistent results with excellent repeatability. By conducting a series of coupled dissolution-permeation experiments with immediate release and sustained release formulations of the same substance, it has been shown that the device can capture the dynamics of drug absorption when the rate-limiting step is either drug release from the dosage form or drug permeation across the membrane. This established the device as a tool for comparing different formulations or generating *in vitro* data that can be later used for *in vivo* correlations. Finally, the possibility to increase the permeation rate by scaling up the total membrane area has been demonstrated. A surface area of 100 cm² made it possible to permeate nearly 20 % of the dose in 120 min, which would be important especially for supersaturating formulations where achieving a sufficiently high absorption rate is considered crucial for obtaining biorelevant *in vitro* data. However, it should be kept in mind that despite the possibility to scale up the permeation area, matching the overall permeation rate with the drug

dissolution rate may still not be possible for formulations where the drug release is very fast.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

David Zúza: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Doreen Pritts:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Vojtěch Klimša:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Josef Beránek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization. **František Štěpánek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgement

D.Z. would like to acknowledge support by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (TAČR), grant number TQ03000729, within the Sigma DC2 programme. The authors gratefully acknowledge support provided by The Pharmaceutical Applied Research Centre. F.Š. would like to acknowledge support by the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius under the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (project no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004597).

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2026.115074>.

Data availability

Research data for this article are available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17854034>.

References

- [1] Z. Li, X. He, S. Tian, G. Feng, C. Huang, M. Xun, Z. Wu, Y. Wang, Simultaneous evaluation of dissolution and permeation of oral drug solid formulations for predicting absorption rate-limiting factors and *in vitro*-*in vivo* correlations: Case study using a poorly soluble weakly basic drug, *AAPS PharmSciTech* 20 (8) (2019) 321.
- [2] M. Kataoka, et al., *In vitro* system to evaluate oral absorption of poorly water-soluble drugs: simultaneous analysis on dissolution and permeation of drugs, *Pharm. Res.* 20 (10) (2003) 1674–1680.
- [3] M. Kataoka, Y. Masaoka, S. Sakuma, S. Yamashita, Effect of food intake on the oral absorption of poorly water-soluble drugs: *In vitro* assessment of drug dissolution and permeation assay system, *J. Pharm. Sci.* 95 (9) (2006) 2051–2061.
- [4] D. Sironi, J. Rosenberg, A. Bauer-Brandl, M. Brandl, PermeaLoop™, a novel *in vitro* tool for small-scale drug-dissolution/permeation studies, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 156 (2018) 247–251.
- [5] E. Borbás, et al., *In vitro* dissolution-permeation evaluation of an electrospun cyclodextrin-based formulation of aripiprazole using $\mu\text{Flux}^{\text{TM}}$, *Int. J. Pharm.* 491 (1) (2015) 180–189.
- [6] J.B. Eriksen, et al., Dissolution/permeation with PermeaLoop™: Experience and *IVIVC* exemplified by dipyrindamole-enabling formulations, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 154 (2020) 105532.
- [7] M. Siewert, FIP guidelines for dissolution testing of solid oral products, *Drug Inf. J.* 30 (4) (1996) 1071–1084.
- [8] United States Pharmacopeial Convention (2011). Chapter (711) Dissolution.
- [9] M. Kansy, F. Senner, K. Gubernator, Physicochemical high-throughput screening: parallel artificial membrane permeation assay in the description of passive absorption processes, *J. Med. Chem.* 41 (7) (1998) 1007–1010.
- [10] I.J. Hidalgo, T.J. Raub, R.T. Borchardt, Characterization of the human colon carcinoma cell line (Caco-2) as a model system for intestinal epithelial permeability, *Gastroenterology* 96 (3) (1989) 736–749.
- [11] J.D. Irvine, et al., MDCK (Madin-Darby Canine Kidney) cells: a tool for membrane permeability screening, *J. Pharm. Sci.* 88 (1) (1999) 28–33.
- [12] P. Berben, et al., Drug permeability pro ling using cell-free permeation tools: Overview and applications, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 119 (2018) 219–233.
- [13] J.T. Lynnerup, T. Lillotte, D. Oversohl, M. Feldmueller, A. Bauer-Brandl, M. Brandl, U. Münster, M. Karl, Can an absorptive sink improve the predictivity of biomimetic

- two-stage dissolution testing? Comparative IVIVC of various formulations of the poorly soluble drug emodepside, *J. Pharm. Sci.* 115 (2026) 104144.
- [14] A. Sitovs, V. Cernisova, V. Mohylyuk, Dissolution-permeation systems in biopharmaceutical research: a graphical review on the current state-of-the-art, *J. Drug Delivery Sci. Technol.* 107 (2025) 106814.
- [15] M. Bermejo, et al., PAMPA—a drug absorption in vitro model: 7. Comparing rat in situ, Caco-2, and PAMPA permeability of fluoroquinolones, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 21 (4) (2004) 429–441.
- [16] V. Gray, et al., The science of USP 1 and 2 dissolution: present challenges and future relevance, *Pharm. Res.* 26 (6) (2009) 1289–1302.
- [17] L. Klumpp, M. Leigh, J. Dressman, Dissolution behavior of various drugs in different FaSSiF versions, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 142 (2020) 105138.
- [18] I. Lozoya-Agullo, et al., Usefulness of Caco-2/HT29-MTX and Caco-2/HT29-MTX/Raji B coculture models to predict intestinal and colonic permeability compared to Caco-2 monoculture, *Mol. Pharm.* 14 (4) (2017) 1264–1270.
- [19] É. Hellinger, et al., Comparison of brain capillary endothelial cell-based and epithelial (MDCK-MDR1, Caco-2, and VB-Caco-2) cell-based surrogate blood–brain barrier penetration models, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 82 (2) (2012) 340–351.
- [20] B. Wang, G. Bredael, P.M. Armenante, Computational hydrodynamic comparison of a mini vessel and a USP 2 dissolution testing system to predict the dynamic operating conditions for similarity of dissolution performance, *Int. J. Pharm.* 539 (1) (2018) 112–130.
- [21] Pion Inc. FLUX Measurements using Pion μ FLUX™ and MacroFLUX™ Devices. Pion Technical Note, TN7010 Rev A 03162017 (2017).
- [22] F.L. Holzem, et al., Combining in vitro dissolution/permeation with microdialysis sampling: Capabilities and limitations for biopharmaceutical assessments of supersaturating drug formulations, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 188 (2023) 106533.
- [23] S. Kádár, et al., Flux-Based Formulation Development—A Proof of Concept Study, *AAPS J.* 24 (2022) 22, doi: 10.1208/s12248-021-00668-9.
- [24] D. Bertoli, et al., A novel MRI-based three-dimensional model of stomach volume, surface area, and geometry in response to gastric filling and emptying, *Neurogastroenterology Motility* 35 (2) (2023) e14497.
- [25] J.P. Wilson, Surface area of the small intestine in man, *Gut* 8 (6) (1967) 618–621.
- [26] H.F. Helander, L. Fändriks, Surface area of the digestive tract – revisited, *Scand. J. Gastroenterol.* 49 (6) (2014) 681–689.
- [27] N. Ward, The impact of intestinal failure on oral drug absorption: a review, *J. Gastrointest. Surg.* 14 (6) (2010) 1045–1051.
- [28] C. Stillhart, et al., Impact of gastrointestinal physiology on drug absorption in special populations—an UNGAP review, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 147 (2020) 105280.
- [29] F.K. Henn, K. Alim, Viscosity's impact on nutrient uptake along the gut, *Phys. Rev. Fluids* 10 (3) (2025) 033103.
- [30] N. Palmada, J.E. Cater, L.K. Cheng, V. Suresh, Anatomically realistic computational model of flow and mixing in the human duodenum, *Phys. Fluids* 35 (1) (2023) 011907.
- [31] D. Dahlgren, M.-J. Cano-Cebrián, T. Olander, M. Hedeland, M. Sjöblom, H. Lennernäs, Regional intestinal drug permeability and effects of permeation enhancers in rat, *Pharmaceutics* 12 (3) (2020) 242.
- [32] A. Avdeef, Absorption and Drug Development: Solubility, Permeability, and Charge State, 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey, 2012.
- [33] P. Tózsér, S. Kádár, E. Szabó, H. Pataki, P. Söti, P. Laczay, G.T. Balogh, B. Sinkó, E. Borbás, Comparison of lipophilic and size-exclusion membranes: Creating sink conditions with cyclodextrin, *ADMET DMPK* 13 (2025) 2859.
- [34] D.W. Green, M.Z. Southard, Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook, 9th ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 2019.
- [35] K. Storchmannová, M. Balouch, J. Juračka, F. Štěpánek, K. Berka, Meta-analysis of permeability literature data shows possibilities and limitations of popular methods, *Mol. Pharm.* 22 (2025) 1293–1304.
- [36] A.C.F. Ribeiro, M.C.F. Barros, V.M.M. Lobo, G. Quintanilla, M.A. Esteso, Diffusion coefficients of the ternary system calcium chloride-caffeine-water at (25 and 37)°C, *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 55 (2010) 897–900.